

Electrochemical reactions at sacrificial electrodes. Part-XX^ψ. Synthesis of coordination compounds of antimony(III) alkoxides

J. S. Banait*, Baljit Singh and Sarbjit Rala

Department of Chemistry, Punjabi University, Patiala-147 002, Punjab, India

Manuscript received 19 October 2006, accepted 27 October 2006

Abstract : Coordination compounds of antimony(III) alkoxides have been synthesised with 1,10-phenanthroline and 2,2'-bipyridyl (L) by electrochemical method. These compounds have been isolated by electrolysis of the solution of alcohol (methanol, ethanol, propan-1-ol, butan-1-ol, pentan-1-ol, hexan-1-ol, heptan-1-ol, octan-1-ol, nonan-1-ol or decan-1-ol) and ligand for ten hours in acetonitrile at antimony anode. The products have been characterized by elemental analysis and infrared spectral studies and conform to general formula, $Sb(OR)_3.L$. Current efficiencies of all these reactions are quite high.

Keywords : Alkoxides, antimony(III), electrochemical reactions.

In continuation to our interest in electrochemical synthesis of inorganic compounds¹, synthesis of antimony(III) alkoxides were reported recently from our laboratory². Generally, metal alkoxides do not form coordination compounds as the metals in alkoxides achieve their favourable coordination number through alkoxy bridging. In the present communication, we report the electrochemical synthesis of the coordination compounds of antimony(III) alkoxides with 1,10-phenanthroline and 2,2'-bipyridyl.

Results and discussion

The antimony(III) alkoxides, reported earlier, have been refluxed with 1,10-phenanthroline and 2,2'-bipyridyl separately in solvents like methanol, ethanol, benzene and acetonitrile for 48 h in order to prepare coordination compounds of these alkoxides. Analytical data and infrared spectral data of these products show that the ligand molecules could not rupture the alkoxy bridges in these antimony(III) alkoxides to form their coordination compounds. It may be due to the reason that the metal in these alkoxides has already achieved its favourable coordination number through alkoxy bridging, therefore, further expansion of coordination sphere due to addition of ligand could not be achieved. It was, thus considered worthwhile that the ligand may be added to these alkoxides before these form alkoxy bridges and get polymerized. Therefore, in addition to alcohol (methanol, ethanol, propan-1-ol, butan-1-ol, pentan-1-ol, hexan-1-ol, heptan-

1-ol, octan-1-ol, nonan-1-ol or decan-1-ol) and supporting electrolyte, 1.0 g of the ligand was also added to these systems and the solution was electrolysed at antimony anode and inert platinum cathode for ten hours.

The products obtained are insoluble in commonly used organic solvents like chloroform, benzene, methanol, acetone, dimethyl sulphoxide, *N,N*-dimethyl formamide etc. Melting point of all these products have also been determined. All these compounds do not melt up to 300 °C, however, colour of these compounds changes around 220 °C, thereby indicating that these products decompose around this temperature. The analytical data (antimony, carbon and hydrogen contents in all the products) conform to the molecular formula $Sb(OR)_3.L$. All the relevant data are summarized in Table 1.

Infrared spectral data of all these products reveal that there is no absorption band corresponding to hydroxyl group³ ($3600-3200\text{ cm}^{-1}$). However, the characteristic bands appear in the region of 580-548, 1161-1020 and 1625-1401 cm^{-1} . $\nu(Sb-O)$ stretching mode^{2,4} in antimony(III) alkoxides appear in the region of 612-540 cm^{-1} . These bands appear in the region of 560-543 cm^{-1} . Thus the bands in the region 580-548 cm^{-1} in the present studies can be assigned to $\nu(Sb-O)$ stretching vibrations. Comparison of the present infrared studies to those of the parent alkoxides shows shift of these bands towards the higher region².

^ψPart-XIX : J. Indian Chem. Soc., (communicated).

Table 1. Electrolysis characteristics, analytical and other related data of electrolytic products of alcohol + ligand systems at antimony anode [Potential : 50 V, current in coulombs : 720]

(a) Ligand : 1,10-Phenanthroline						
System	Product	Colour	Elemental analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)			Current efficiency (gram equivalent/Faraday)
			Sb	C	H	
Methanol	$C_3H_9O_3SbC_{12}H_8N_2$	Dirty white	31.9 (30.7)	40.5 (45.6)	2.45 (4.30)	0.95
Ethanol	$C_6H_{15}O_3SbC_{12}H_8N_2$	Dirty white	27.4 (27.7)	46.8 (49.5)	3.80 (5.27)	0.84
Propan-1-ol	$C_9H_{21}O_3SbC_{12}H_8N_2$	Light brown	25.8 (25.4)	49.5 (53.0)	5.46 (6.73)	0.90
Butan-1-ol	$C_{12}H_{27}O_3SbC_{12}H_8N_2$	Light brown	22.8 (23.6)	54.7 (55.3)	5.63 (6.73)	0.92
Pentan-1-ol	$C_{15}H_{33}O_3SbC_{12}H_8N_2$	Light brown	21.1 (21.5)	55.4 (57.6)	6.24 (7.29)	0.86
Hexan-1-ol	$C_{18}H_{39}O_3SbC_{12}H_8N_2$	Light brown	21.1 (21.5)	55.7 (59.3)	7.04 (7.74)	0.92
Heptan-1-ol	$C_{21}H_{45}O_3SbC_{12}H_8N_2$	Light brown	18.0 (18.7)	85.4 (61.4)	7.89 (8.22)	0.75
Octan-1-ol	$C_{24}H_{51}O_3SbC_{12}H_8N_2$	Light brown	16.7 (17.5)	61.3 (62.7)	8.21 (8.57)	0.83
Nonan-1-ol	$C_{27}H_{57}O_3SbC_{12}H_8N_2$	Light brown	16.8 (16.5)	62.8 (64.1)	8.45 (8.90)	0.87
Decan-1-ol	$C_{30}H_{63}O_3SbC_{12}H_8N_2$	Light brown	15.1 (15.7)	64.9 (65.2)	8.73 (9.19)	0.92
(b) Ligand : 2,2'-Bipyridyl						
Methanol	$C_3H_9O_3SbC_{10}H_8N_2$	Light brown	31.9 (32.7)	39.4 (42.1)	3.27 (4.59)	0.96
Ethanol	$C_6H_{15}O_3SbC_{10}H_8N_2$	Light brown	30.4 (29.3)	45.7 (46.4)	5.03 (5.58)	0.89
Propan-1-ol	$C_9H_{21}O_3SbC_{10}H_8N_2$	Light brown	27.4 (26.6)	48.5 (50.2)	6.21 (6.38)	0.84
Butan-1-ol	$C_{12}H_{27}O_3SbC_{10}H_8N_2$	Light brown	25.8 (24.3)	50.4 (53.2)	6.73 (7.05)	0.90
Pentan-1-ol	$C_{15}H_{33}O_3SbC_{10}H_8N_2$	Light brown	22.8 (22.4)	54.6 (55.7)	7.47 (7.62)	0.97
Hexan-1-ol	$C_{18}H_{39}O_3SbC_{10}H_8N_2$	Light brown	21.1 (20.8)	53.4 (57.9)	7.94 (8.10)	0.64
Heptan-1-ol	$C_{21}H_{45}O_3SbC_{10}H_8N_2$	Light brown	18.2 (19.4)	58.1 (59.8)	8.52 (8.52)	0.71
Octan-1-ol	$C_{24}H_{51}O_3SbC_{10}H_8N_2$	Light brown	18.0 (18.5)	60.7 (61.8)	8.74 (8.88)	0.92
Nonan-1-ol	$C_{27}H_{57}O_3SbC_{10}H_8N_2$	Light brown	18.1 (17.1)	61.4 (62.8)	8.93 (9.20)	0.78
Decan-1-ol	$C_{30}H_{65}O_3SbC_{10}H_8N_2$	Light brown	16.7 (16.2)	63.8 (64.1)	9.27 (9.49)	0.93

Infrared bands in 1161–1020 cm^{-1} region have been assigned to $\nu(\text{C-O})\text{M}$ stretching vibrations⁵. The bands in the region 1161–1060 cm^{-1} are assigned to terminal alkoxide groups and those in 1060–1020 cm^{-1} region are due to bridged alkoxide groups. In the present studies these bands, however, appear in the region of 1161–1020 cm^{-1} and distinct two or three bands are observed in this region. In the parent alkoxides these bands appear in 1160–1000 cm^{-1} region thereby showing a shift of these bands also to higher region in the present studies. The bands in the region of 1625–1401 cm^{-1} are due to ligand molecules as no such bands were observed in the infrared spectra of the parent alkoxides². These bands can be assigned to $\nu(\text{C}\cdots\text{C})$ and $\nu(\text{C}\cdots\text{N})$ stretching modes. These bands, however, appear in slightly lower region as compared to those in the pure ligand.

Appearance of $\nu(\text{C-O})\text{Sb}$ and $\nu(\text{Sb-O})$ absorption bands and absence of bands due to hydroxyl group in the present products indicate that the protons of the alcohol molecules have been replaced by anodic antimony to yield antimony(III) alkoxides. Shift of the $\nu(\text{C-O})\text{Sb}$ and $\nu(\text{Sb-O})$ absorption bands towards the higher region as compared to those in parent alkoxides and appearance of the bands ($\nu(\text{C}\cdots\text{C})$ and $\nu(\text{C}\cdots\text{N})$) due to ligand molecules show that the present products are the coordination compounds of antimony(III) alkoxides. Solubility, melting point and infrared spectral data of the products indicate their polymeric nature through alkoxy bridging.

Current efficiencies of all these reactions have been determined and the data are listed in Table 1. Perusal of Table 1 reveals that the current efficiencies of these systems are quite high thereby showing that the reactions leading to the formation of coordination compounds of antimony(III) alkoxides are the predominant reactions of these systems. The reaction scheme can thus be given as :

At cathode :

At anode :

The present electrochemical technique presents a direct route for the synthesis of coordination compounds of antimony(III) alkoxides which are otherwise difficult to prepare through conventional methods. In addition, the present synthetic method is single-pot, single-step and can be conducted by using routine laboratory chemicals and equipment.

Experimental

Acetonitrile was kept over phosphorus pentoxide for 24 h and then double distilled. Freshly distilled acetonitrile was used as solvent in all these reactions. Tetrabutylammonium chloride was used as supporting electrolyte, which was crystallized from conductivity water and dried under reduced pressure at 100 °C. Electrolysis of the alcohol (2 mL), acetonitrile (250 mL), ligand (1.0 g) and tetrabutylammonium chloride (1.0 g) was carried out in H-type cell made up of pyrex glass in which cathode and anode compartments were separated from each other by sintered glass disc of G-3 porosity. Both compartments were provided with two openings, one for guard tube and the other for electrode. Platinum foil ($1.0 \times 1.0 \text{ cm}^2$) and antimony plate ($2 \times 10 \times 0.2 \text{ cm}^3$) were used as cathode and anode respectively. Direct current was obtained with the help of Toshniwal electrophoresis power supply. The electrolytic solution was stirred efficiently using magnetic stirrer. The electrolytic cell can be represented as :

where, $\text{Sb}_{(+)}$ is antimony anode, $\text{Pt}_{(-)}$ is platinum cathode, L represents 1,10-phenanthroline or 2,2'-bipyridyl.

Electrolysis has been carried out for ten hours at a constant current of 20 mA. The solid products separated in anode compartment after electrolysis were filtered in filtration unit of G-3 porosity and washed with hot acetonitrile and dry ether and dried under vacuum. Melting point of all these products were recorded using electrical device with a heating rate of 5 °C per minute. Antimony contents in all these products were determined volumetrically⁶. Microanalysis for carbon and hydrogen contents of these products have also been carried out. Infrared spectra of the products have been recorded using potassium bromide pellets and Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer (RXI) in the region of 4000–450 cm^{-1} .

The current efficiencies (gram equivalents of metal dissolved per Faraday) of all these reactions were determined by electrolysis of the above systems for exactly two hours at a constant current of 20 mA. The solution of anode compartment was taken out. The anode and anode compartment were washed with acetonitrile and washings were mixed with the anodic solution. Solvent from this solution was distilled in a film evaporator and antimony content in the residue was determined volumetrically as reported earlier^{2,6}. The ratio of experimental and theo-

retical antimony contents gives the current efficiency of the system.

References

1. J. S. Banait, S. K. Deol and Baljit Singh, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1990, **20**, 1331; J. S. Banait, Rani Devi and Baljit Singh, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1991, **64**, 3669; J. S. Banait, Neeru Arora and Baljit Singh, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 2000, **49**, 10; J. S. Banait and Baljit Singh, *J. Electrochem. Soc. India*, 2001, **50**, 76; J. S. Banait, Baljit Singh and Harpreet Kaur, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **82**, 1.
2. J. S. Banait, Baljit Singh and Sarbjit Rala, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (communicated).
3. M. Avram and G. Mattescu, "Infrared Spectroscopy Application in Organic Compounds", William Interscience, New York, 1972; J. R. Dyer's, "Application of Absorption Spectroscopy of Organic Compounds", Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi, 1962.
4. T. B. Brill and N. C. Campbell, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1973, **12**, 1884.
5. C. G. Barraclough, D. C. Bradley, J. Lewis and I. M. Thomas, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 2601; R. W. Adams, R. L. Martin and G. Winter, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1967, **20**, 733; G. A. Kakos and G. Winter, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1969, **22**, 97; L. Dubicki, G. A. Kakos and G. Winter, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1968, **21**, 1468; R. W. Adams, C. G. Barraclough, R. L. Martin and G. Winter, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1967, **20**, 2351; C. H. Brubaker (Jr.) and M. Nicholas, *Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1965, **27**, 59.
6. Vogel's, "Text Book of Quantitative Chemical Analysis", Longman Group UK, Ltd., 1989, p. 397.